

Isoquinoline Derivatives : Part XXII*. Synthesis of 1-(β -Aminoethyl)-1, 2, 3, 4-Tetrahydroisoquinoline and 1, 1'-Alkyl (or Aryl)-Methylene-bis-3-Alkyl (or Aryl)-3, 4-Dihydroisoquinolines

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N- β -Phenethyl-cyanoacetamide, on cyclisation with P_2O_5 in boiling toluene afforded 1-cyanomethyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline which was reduced with sodium and ethanol to yield 1-(β -aminoethyl)-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinoline. Some alkyl- and aryl malondi- α -alkyl (or aryl)- β -phenethylamides have been prepared and cyclised with P_2O_5 in boiling toluene to yield the corresponding 1, 1'-alkyl (or aryl)-methylene-bis-3-alkyl (or aryl)-3, 4-dihydroisoquinolines.

In an earlier communication¹, the synthesis of 1-(β -aminoethyl)-3-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinoline was reported. The series has been extended in order to include a compound which does not carry a methyl group at the 3-position of the isoquinoline ring. With such an objective *N*- β -phenethyl-cyanoacetamide² was cyclised with P_2O_5 in boiling

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1. T. N. Ghosh, S. K. Ganguly and B. Bhattacharya, *Jour. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1959, **36**, 699.
2. N. J. Leonard and J. H. Boyer, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 2980.

toluene to furnish 1-cyanomethyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline (I). It may be noted that Leonard and Boyer², on cyclising the same amide with PPA, obtained 1-methyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline; this involved cyclodehydration, hydrolysis and simultaneous decarboxylation. The compound (I) was subsequently reduced with sodium and ethanol^{3,4} to furnish 1-(β -aminoethyl)-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (II).

As an extension of this work an attempt was made to synthesise 1-(β -aminopropyl)-3-methyl-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinoline. With this object in view 1-cyanomethyl-3-methyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline⁴ was subjected to Stephen aldehyde synthesis⁵ so as to furnish the corresponding 1-acetaldehydro-3-methyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline which on reacting with nitromethane and subsequent reduction might afford the desired compound. But the basic product, isolated after Stephen's reaction was identified as 1, 3-dimethyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline⁶ instead of the expected acetaldehydro compound.

The observation, as reported earlier⁷, that 1, 1'-methylene-bis-3-methyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline (IV, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = CH_3$), which, however, exists in the form (V, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = CH_3$), shows appreciable amoebicidal activity *in vivo*, stimulated preparation of some more compounds in this series. The malondiamides, (III, $R_1 = R_2 = C_2H_5$), (III, $R_1 = C_6H_5$, $R_2 = CH_3$) and (III, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = C_6H_5$), were cyclised with P_2O_5 in boiling toluene to yield the corresponding isoquinoline derivatives (VI).

EXPERIMENTAL

1-Cyanomethyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline(I): A mixture of N- β -phenethyl-cyanoacetamide² (10 g) and P_2O_5 (40 g) in toluene (200 ml) was refluxed under stirring in an oil-bath for 4 hrs. The mixture was cooled, treated with water and washed with ether. The aqueous layer, on basification with caustic soda, furnished a solid which was crystallised from aqueous ethanol in cream coloured microcrystalline powder, m.p. 95-96°. (Found: C, 77.22; H, 5.73; N, 16.33. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2$ requires C, 77.64; H, 5.88; N, 16.47%). The picrate was crystallised from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 181-182°. (Found: N, 17.31. $C_{11}H_{10}N_2$, $C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires N, 17.54%).

1-(β -Aminoethyl)-1, 2, 3, 4-tetrahydroisoquinoline (II): Sodium (3 g) was slowly added under stirring to a solution of (I, 3 g) in ethanol (100 ml) and the mixture was gently heated under reflux to dissolve all the sodium. The mixture was cooled and diluted with water (100 ml.). The liquid was distilled off and the residue extracted with HCl (dil.) and precipitated by alkali. By addition of ether to an ethanolic solution of the base, saturated with dry hydrogen chloride, the *dihydrochloride* was obtained as a white crystalline powder, m.p. 245-246°. (Found: N, 11.14; Cl, 28.31. $C_{11}H_{16}N_2$, 2HCl requires N, 11.24; Cl, 28.51%.)

Attempted synthesis of 1-acetaldehydro-3-methyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline by Stephen's method: Formation of 1, 3-dimethyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline: To a suspension of anhydrous stannous chloride (26 g) in anhydrous ether (250 ml), saturated with dry hydrogen

3. L. A. Walter and S. M. McElvain, *ibid.*, 1934, 56, 1614.

4. M. S. Bloom, D. S. Breslow and C. R. Hauser, *ibid.*, 1945, 67, 539.

5. H. Stephen, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1925, 1874.

6. D. H. Hey, *ibid.*, 1930, 18.,

chloride, was slowly added a solution of 1-cyanomethyl-3-methyl-3,4-dihydroisoquinoline (12 g) in anhydrous ether (50 ml) in ice-cold condition under mechanical stirring. The stirring was continued for 3 hrs more and the solid thus formed was filtered and decomposed with hot water. After removal of tin by hydrogen sulphide, the final acidic solution was basified in cold to afford a gummy product, which was characterised as its picrate, m.p. 135-136°. This was subsequently identified as the picrate of 1, 3-dimethyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline by m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic sample⁶. (Found : C, 52.51 ; H, 4.16; N, 14.33. Calc. for $C_{11}H_{13}N$, $C_6H_3N_3O_7$: C, 52.57; H, 4.12; N, 14.43%).

Ethylmalondi- α -ethyl- β -phenethylamide (III, $R_1 = R_2 = C_2H_5$): This compound was prepared in the manner reported earlier⁷ from ethyl ethylmalonate (9.4 g) and α -ethyl- β -phenethylamine (14.9 g) and was crystallised from ethanol in colourless plates (12.5 g), m.p. 98-99°. (Found : N, 7.48. $C_{25}H_{34}N_2O_2$ requires N, 7.10%).

1, 1'-*Ethylmethylene-bis-3 ethyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline* (IV, $R_1 = R_2 = C_2H_5$): A mixture of (III, $R_1 = R_2 = C_2H_5$; 10 g) and P_2O_5 (40 g) in toluene (200 ml) was refluxed in an oil-bath under mechanical stirring for 4 hrs. The mixture was cooled and treated with ice-water. The aqueous layer was separated, washed with ether and basified with caustic soda to yield a base (1.4 g) which was characterised as dipicrate, crystallising from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 154-155°. (Found : C, 54.63; H, 4.52; N, 13.93. $C_{25}H_{30}N_2$, $2C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires C, 54.41; H, 4.41; N, 13.72%).

Phenylmalondi- α -methyl- β -phenethylamide (III, $R_1 = C_6H_5$, $R_2 = CH_3$). This amide (15.2 g) was obtained from ethyl phenyl malonate⁸ (11.8 g) and α -methyl- β -phenethylamine⁹ (13.5 g) according to the procedure reported earlier⁷ and was crystallised from dilute ethanol in plates, m.p. 139-140°. (Found : N, 6.72. $C_{27}H_{30}N_2O_2$ requires N, 6.76%).

1, 1'-*Phenyl methylene-bis-3-methylisoquinoline* (VI, $R_1 = C_6H_5$, $R_2 = CH_3$): A mixture of (III, $R_1 = C_6H_5$, $R_2 = CH_3$; 15 g) and P_2O_5 (60 g) in toluene (300 ml) was refluxed for 4 hrs. under mechanical stirring in an oil-bath. The mixture was worked up, as described above, to furnish a crude base (1.5 g) which could not be characterised by forming any salt. It was dehydrogenated, in the usual way, by heating over Pd-C (10%) at 240° in tetralin for 4 hrs. The aromatised base was characterised as *dipicrate*, crystallising from ethanol in yellow needles, m.p. 186-187°. (Found : C, 56.05; H, 3.13; N, 13.31. $C_{27}H_{22}N_2$, $2C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires C, 56.25; H, 3.36; N, 13.46%).

1, 1'-*Methylene-bis-3-phenyl-3, 4-dihydroisoquinoline* (IV, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = C_6H_5$): This was prepared in the manner as described above, by treating malondi- α , β -diphenethylamide (III, $R_1 = H$, $R_2 = C_6H_5$)⁷, with P_2O_5 in toluene. The base was characterised as dipicrate, m.p. 215-216°. (Found : C, 58.18; H, 3.56; N, 12.93. $C_{31}H_{26}N_2$, $2C_6H_3N_3O_7$ requires C, 58.37; H, 3.61; N, 12.66%).

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9. O. Y. Magidson and G. A. Garkusha, *J. Gen. Chem. (U.S.S.R.)*, 1941, **11**, 339; *Chem. Abstr.*, 1941, **35**, 5868.